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Wang Ping, Zheng Hanyue

Abstract

Earlier this year, writing about art and image-generating technologies with artificial intelligence had a huge impact on art scholars and artists. These technologies have also drawn attention to the current status of digital development in Chinese fine arts. In fact, digital research and research and development projects on Chinese fine arts have been underway for over a decade. Numerous research institutes and scholars have focused their research on areas such as the digitization of art images and the mapping of art knowledge. They have achieved many significant results. However, compared to Europe and the United States, the digitization foundation of Chinese fine arts still has many deficiencies and lags, which constrain the cross-media and cross-cultural dissemination and application of Chinese art and culture.

Key Words

Chinese art, knowledge graph, digitization, image, knowledge system

1. What is Digitizing Art Images?

In recent years, the text-to-image generation technology of artificial intelligence (AI) has caused a significant shockwave in China's art field. On one hand, people are astonished that AI can generate images based solely on textual descriptions; on the other hand, they worry whether AI might eventually overwhelm and replace some artistic works, especially since some art exhibitions have already featured works aided by AI which seem to demonstrate a certain level of transcendence in terms of pictorial formation. However, image generation and text-to-graph generation are not novel techniques for researchers who focused on image digitization prior to 2014. At the same time, while observing various types of Chinese painting images generated by AI published on streaming media platforms, it is regrettable and concerning to note that the development of the knowledge graph of Chinese art underlying the databases of domestic and international Large Models is still lagging. Despite their expertise, many scholars are not privy to the development and current status of the digitization of art images in China.

In this section, the term "digitization of art images" is defined, as is the research and application of digitization. The digitization of art images is a process that involves the scanning, identification, and labeling of art images on artwork and printed materials using digital cameras. The resulting data is then stored for future reference. Additionally, the digitization of art images has led to the development of specialized tools for the classification, genealogization, and networking of art image data by experts and data engineers. These tools facilitate the establishment of structured database systems, enabling efficient searching, analysis, and output of information. On top of this, the research and application of art image digitization is predicated on activities of knowledge research, learning, production, and generation of art images based on art image databases.

2. Development Status of Databases of Chinese Art Knowledge

Databases represent the foundation of any research and application project involving digitization. In August

2019, Chinese government departments issued a guiding document on “Promoting the Deep Integration of Culture and Science and Technology.”¹ In recent years, the government has hoped that researchers would use digitization technology to label the cultural genes (outstanding cultural symbols) found in the collections of museums, art galleries, schools, and other public cultural institutions. This work will boost cultural confidence and promote the global spread of Chinese culture. In 2020, the Dunhuang Research Institute, the Hunan Provincial Museum, Zhejiang University, Tsinghua University, and Wuhan University jointly opened a national key research project: Research and Development of Key Technologies for Cultural Relics Knowledge Organization and Services Based on Knowledge Maps; the Shanghai Museum is undertaking the Research and Demonstration of Key Technologies for Aggregation and Dissemination of Cultural Relics Knowledge project. These two projects have published several research results indicating that a database of knowledge about images of Chinese cultural relics will likely be released in the near future.

Currently, few scholars and projects within the art discipline have undertaken the task of digitizing Chinese art images and developing databases. Opinions from scholars on the feasibility of digitizing Chinese art images, the progress of ongoing projects, and the publication of their results can be found in the booklet *World 3: A Library of Pictorial Literature*, edited by Wu Hong. This publication shows that preliminary achievements have been made in the research on indexing and annotating knowledge of Chinese art images. These achievements are primarily represented by The Images Database of Han China project, led by Zhu Qingsheng from Peking University, and The Chinese Iconography Thesaurus (CIT), directed by Zhang Hongxing. Additionally, the Palace Museums in Beijing and Taipei have conducted related research, though their findings have not been made publicly accessible. Notably, the book reveals that the lack of foundational studies and developmental lag in this field have drawn significant attention from the academic community of art historians.

From a technical perspective, research on the digitization of Chinese art images for Chinese art within the field of information resource management began around 2019.² One notable study is the paper “Design and Application Research of a Knowledge Graph Centered on Farming and Weaving Images” by Xie Wei and Yang Jiayao, which proposed a comprehensive framework. The framework uses farming and weaving images from various artistic forms as data sources to

create a database of image materials, and then builds an ontology-based knowledge graph to enable in-depth image mining and to meet knowledge service requirements.³ Zhidong Zhang and his research team conducted a pioneering study in which they used “meta-painting” works from the Ming Dynasty as examples. The semantic information of these works was described from six aspects: graphic meaning, scene layout, storyline, characters, painting-within-a-painting, and the artist’s aesthetic emotion. Based on this multidimensional analysis, the team proposed a specialized metadata framework for meta-paintings. They also developed an ontology-based artwork model that incorporates linked data principles and established a knowledge-linked organizational model for artistic works. This methodological innovation provides valuable references for advancing semantic description techniques in art research, enhancing knowledge linkage frameworks for cultural heritage digitization, and complementing existing approaches to artwork knowledge representation.⁴

Additionally, some dissertations explore the technological path of knowledge graph construction by taking Thangka, ancient paintings, porcelain, and modern and contemporary artists as their subjects; Zhang Na created a knowledge graph system focusing on Huang Binhong’s artworks. This system is driven by an ontology research project on key technologies and applications of cultural relics knowledge graph construction. Its precision is verified through the assessments of museum professionals and real-world applications.

3. The Value of Knowledge Annotation and Database Construction for Art Images

Contemporary AI can be categorized into two technical frameworks. One involves simulating human brain neural networks using computers, represented by deep neural networks, the other focuses on simulating human cognition by recording brain-derived memories and presenting knowledge in graphical form, represented by knowledge graphs. The former focuses on perception, recognition and judgment techniques, while the latter emphasizes cognition, language and knowledge processing. Current AI development indicates that although deep learning performs robustly in perception tasks such as vision and hearing, it still relies on knowledge graphs for thinking, reasoning, and language understanding. In other words, while AI can technically distinguish between photographs and paintings,

recognizing and interpreting a painting's content and meaning requires knowledge graphs constructed by human experts. From the perspective of AI, humans accumulate knowledge through cognition and practice, then apply this learned knowledge to solve problems in life and work. Human natural language, along with created artworks (paintings, music), mathematical notation, physical models, and chemical formulas all serve as carriers for representing and transmitting human knowledge.⁵

In reality, most human knowledge is recorded and passed down through written symbols of natural language, which is represented by written symbols. Therefore, in the traditional field of AI, there is a classic research direction—knowledge engineering and expert systems. So-called knowledge engineering relies on experts to systematically organize, express, store, and apply knowledge within a specific discipline so that computers can solve complex problems in that field as experts do.⁶ However, as the internet has developed and the scope of knowledge acquisition has expanded, single expert systems have begun to expand their scope to cover broader areas of knowledge management and intelligent information processing. Google proposed the knowledge graph technology and applied it to its search engine in 2012. Essentially, a knowledge graph refers to a structured knowledge representation method based on a directed labeled graph, aiming to utilize graph structure for modeling, identification, the inference of complex relationships between things and to accumulate domain knowledge.⁷ It is like a vast knowledge map, connecting various pieces of information through entities and relationships, allowing people to clearly see the connections between different knowledge elements, and thereby enabling a better understanding and utilization of knowledge.⁸ Knowledge graphs are often used to support semantic search, intelligent question and answer, recommendation systems (presenting multiple relationship networks in things or texts) to assist in language semantic understanding, expand the depth and breadth of visual understanding, and support the interconnection and big data analysis, etc.

From a technologist's point of view, the process of digitizing cultural heritage for specific areas of expertise nowadays focuses mainly on automatically identifying and extracting knowledge. This is because traditional knowledge acquisition is carried out through manual annotation and coding. To obtain the various new types of knowledge that are being explosively generated at present, as well as the universal knowledge contained in historical documents, is impossible to achieve through manual means. Although deep learning technology

has made significant progress in automatic recognition and automatic clustering, this still occurs at the perceptual level and is merely equivalent to human sensory perception of things. At the cognitive and expressive levels human assistance is still necessary, or rather the accumulated knowledge system construction achievements of humans over the past century are. In other words, if we want AI to automatically identify a painting, further identify various objects in the picture, and then further determine the theme and narrative of the painting as well as the artists and other related works, this requires the use of knowledge graphs or expert systems (藝術詞典或圖像志索引系統).

4. The Process of Data Mining Art Images is the Construction of Visual Knowledge about the World

For art, the utility and value of art image data extends beyond merely supporting semantic search, intelligent question answering, and recommendation systems at the network level. More importantly, their value lies in expanding the depth and breadth of visual understanding. Specifically speaking, whether it is an ordinary viewer or an art researcher, when viewing a painting what is immediately perceived is merely a simple image, and in terms of meaning comprehension it has little difference from an animal photo. However, if one wants to view the picture at the cognitive understanding level, or to describe the content of the picture in terms of language, such as observing, identifying and understanding the various plants and animals, rocks, trees, themes, narratives, techniques and materials in the picture, it is a process of gradual expansion. At the same time, this process also requires certain knowledge in a specific professional field. The value of knowledge graphs in expanding the depth and breadth of visual understanding is primarily reflected in the process of converting analog images into digital information for computer storage. To enable programs to automatically identify the knowledge embedded in images, knowledge identification and extraction must first be conducted. This process has led to a new understanding of image forms, including semantic networks, visual layers, object layers, and concept layers. Image has become a system for expressing knowledge; in other words, directly contributing to the elevation of the visual culture civilization form and giving a value on par with that of language culture. Of course, from the perspective of the development history of academia and technology, the transformation in people's understanding of the depth and breadth of images was not brought about by digital

and information technology. In the field of art studies, its origin can be traced back to the *Iconologia* written by the Italian scholar Cesare Ripa in the sixteenth century, as well as the European image studies tradition represented by scholars such as Riegl, Wofflin, Warburg, Panofsky, and Gombrich since the nineteenth century. However, iconology remains primarily oriented towards symbolic interpretation of images. In contrast, the digitization and informatization of printed materials, driven by digital and information technology, have advanced image semantics from symbol to expression. At the stage of knowledge graph technology, methods such as vector representation and big data-based semantic networks have enabled the gradual verification and structuring of knowledge within artistic imagery.

Due to the limitations of disciplines and technologies, those in Chinese art generally have a limited understanding of big data and artificial intelligence technologies, as do the researchers involved in this field. Looking around the world, major internet technology and data companies in Europe and the United States are all committed to the research and development of image technology. For instance, Google and Wikipedia have both established very large and highly academic-level art knowledge graphs, and art historians and research institutions in Europe and the United States had already established an art image classification and knowledge system in the 1990s.⁹ Regarding the classification of artistic images and the knowledge system of Chinese art, major domestic search engines such as Baidu, Tencent and Sogou have all established knowledge graphs with over hundreds of billions of nodes. However, in the field of knowledge graphs for Chinese art images, it is worthy of our deep reflection that the knowledge search and question-answering functions related to Chinese art images, as well as academic content, are still very scarce, and they are not even as good as Wikipedia's. In the field of art studies, Taiwan was the first to introduce the Dictionary of Western Art and Architecture (AAT) of the Getty Research Institute (GRI). Based on this knowledge framework, it expanded into the Chinese Art and Architecture Dictionary (AAT-Taiwan). However, because it indexed Chinese art knowledge within the framework of the AAT, and the classification and qualitative aspects of a large number of knowledge concepts were somewhat ambiguous, this system has never been accepted by the academic community. On October 12, 2019, the Chinese Iconography Thesaurus (CIT), developed by the British-Chinese scholar Zhang Hongxing, was released at the Beijing Center of the University of Chicago.¹⁰ This knowledge index scheme takes the titles of Qing Palace painting and calligraphy

catalogues, such as *Shi Qu Bao Ji* (《石渠寶笈》) and *MI Dian Zhu Lin* (《秘殿珠林》), as the primary sources of keywords, possessing the original nature of culture. It can be regarded as the pioneering work of the knowledge index for Chinese art images. However, based on the current references and usage statistics of search and knowledge service platforms at home and abroad, there is little attention to, and usage of, them. This may not be solely attributed to the fact that its service targets are mainly museum institutions. Rather, it is because the CIT still employs the knowledge representation method of the traditional expert system era, which is not applicable to the generation of knowledge for the public. However, to some extent it also reflects the cognitive attitude of the domestic technology and knowledge service field towards the cultural value and academic nature of Chinese art images.

From the search on major domestic knowledge graph platforms, it can be seen that there is currently no dedicated Chinese art knowledge graph. However, some AI platforms and AI generated content (AIGC) tools, such as ERNIE Bot, Qiyu AI, and Dreamina, can generate various types of artistic images through the text-to-image method. The technical essence of this is “to establish a cross-modal mapping relationship between text and images through a deep learning model, combined with a generation model (such as a diffusion model) and an attention mechanism, converting natural language description (text) into semantically consistent visual images.” The core lies in establishing a deep connection between text and images and synthesizing new pixel data based on a probability model, relying on the synergy of multimodal learning, large-scale pre-training, and efficient generation algorithms.¹¹ That is to say, the foundation of AIGC image generation lies in large datasets of text and images. To generate high-quality pictures, it is necessary to have multimodal data and structured knowledge to support the completion of large-scale pre-training and to rely on high-quality knowledge graphs. Due to the lack of a high-level knowledge graph for Chinese art images, currently the Chinese art images generated by various AIGC can only be simulated in a simple form, and cannot achieve Chinese-style construction at the level of image structure and thematic narrative. In technical terms of knowledge graphs, AI is still unable to conduct knowledge reasoning and answer using Chinese art images and knowledge.

5. Attention and Application of Art Image Data and AI Technology in China's Education Sector

Art image knowledge databases constitute high-quality data resources. Accumulating such data is a domain of knowledge engineering that requires continuous investment, as it enables the gradual accumulation of disciplinary knowledge.¹² Presently, the absence of an academically valuable Chinese art knowledge database hinders the utilization of reliable professional data and related technologies in art education. However, general-purpose knowledge mapping technologies and image data annotation techniques have been applied to a limited extent in art research and education, simultaneously providing resources and impetus for the digitization of Chinese art knowledge.

Knowledge graph technology, comprising components such as knowledge representation, storage, extraction, fusion, reasoning, question answering, and analysis has brought about significant enlightenment and transformation in art education—particularly through knowledge representation techniques. Traditionally, images and artworks were not regarded as knowledge. In current art education, aside from art history and appreciation courses, most colleges offer few courses focusing on image-related knowledge, and art technique courses are rarely treated as knowledge systems. From the perspectives of knowledge cognition and informatics, any information that can be structured, interpreted, reused, and instructive qualifies as knowledge. With the development of image recognition and big data technologies, the value of visual culture has become increasingly prominent, shifting people's perceptions of images. A painting is not merely a visual representation but a semantic network rich in information: taking the painting as the core, its subjects, themes, narratives, materials, and techniques constitute core entity elements, while art history, collection contexts, and aesthetic analyses serve as peripheral information. This implies that the core of art lies in the image, and art studies should be grounded in the knowledge and technical experience system within the image.

Consequently, although existing knowledge maps for art education are lacking, teachers should attempt to sort out course knowledge elements, construct course knowledge frameworks, and leverage knowledge mapping tools in teaching. The technical requirements for using free knowledge graph tools are relatively undemanding; the key lies in users' knowledge accumulation. For students, it is crucial to recognize diverse knowledge forms, understand art fundamentals and disciplinary significance, and develop the awareness

to structure knowledge and continuously accumulate personal data—a vital capability for their future careers.

Undoubtedly, image generation and AI-assisted writing technologies currently garner the most attention from teachers and students in art teacher training programs, as they assist in artistic creation and academic writing. Technically, these tools have become increasingly user-friendly, lowering technical barriers and enhancing the knowledge value of output data. However, it is essential to recognize that AI is a tool whose value depends on users. When using large models for image and text generation, suboptimal results are often attributed to insufficient AI capability, yet few acknowledge the “Garbage In, Garbage Out” principle in computer science and data analysis. Even as general large model knowledge graphs expand rapidly, answering professional questions hinges on the correctness and precision of queries and input data. This underscores the importance in art education of mastering subject knowledge concepts, understanding knowledge structures, and cultivating logical thinking, analytical skills, and familiarity with reasoning models—abilities that students must acquire in the AI era. While formal logic specialization may not be feasible for students training to be art teachers, practical engagement can facilitate their understanding of knowledge fusion and knowledge reasoning in knowledge mapping processes.

6. Conclusion

Due to China's late start in computer science and data analysis compared to Europe and the United States, the digitization of cultural heritage and the systematic development of visual culture studies have also lagged behind. While art scholars have made concerted efforts since the 1980s to bridge this gap, fundamental challenges persist—particularly in constructing Chinese art knowledge graphs. Moreover, the implicit hegemony shaped by internet and digital standards continues to constrain the development and global dissemination of Chinese culture. In the current era of the explosion of artificial intelligence, we still need to clearly recognize the potential risks caused by that weak foundation. Human civilization is undergoing a transformation from printed press to digital media. The rapid development of AI technology cannot make up for the shortcomings in digital resource infrastructure. The construction research of the Chinese art knowledge graph is the mission and responsibility of scholars in the field of Chinese art, not only in academic research but also in current art education.

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ENDNOTES

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6. *Ibid.*, 60.

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中國美術圖像的數字化研究與現狀

王平，鄭涵月

摘要：在人工智能興起的當下，AI 介入的藝術研究和圖文生成技術對藝術理論研究者和藝術創作者帶來了巨大的衝擊，也引發了人們對中國美術的數字化現狀的關注。事實上，中國美術的數字化研究與研發工程已有數十年的進程，眾多研究機構和學者的研究聚焦於藝術圖像的數字化和藝術知識圖譜等領域，已取得了許多重要成果。但相比歐美地區，中國美術的數字化研究依然存在諸多不足與滯後，這對中國藝術文化的跨媒介、跨文化傳播與應用都有一定的制約。

關鍵詞：中國美術；數字化；圖像；知識圖譜